

Impact of Foliage on Urban MmWave Wireless Propagation Channel: A Ray-tracing Based Analysis

Songjiang Yang, Jiliang Zhang, Jie Zhang

Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering, University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK

Abstract—The foliage has a significant impact on wireless communications under the millimeter wave band. Ray-tracing is a widely used technique to build an accurate wireless channel model. A drawback of ray-tracing is its high complexity. Therefore, using the ray-tracing method to build channel model with complex scatterers like trees results in a high computational burden. In this paper, we propose a hybrid ray-tracing based channel model for wireless channel simulation under typical urban scenario. In the proposed hybrid channel model, the correlation-based channel model is employed to model complex scatterers, e.g., trees, to reduce the computational complexity. Numerical results show that the hybrid model can capture the foliage influence on the wireless channel at the millimeter wave band well.

Index Terms—mmWave, foliage, correlation-based channel model, ray-tracing, radio propagation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Owing to the consideration of millimeter wave (mmWave) frequency allocation for the 5G network, a reliable scattering model for foliage in the urban area becomes urgent because the foliage may influence mmWave propagation channel significantly. The reason for the significant impact of tree on mmWave propagation is that the size of leaves and smaller branches in the tree becomes comparable to the mmWave propagation signal wavelength [1]. A utilitarian channel model should have a trade-off between accuracy and computational burden. From an accuracy of channel model perspective, the ray-tracing method is a widely-used method to build the channel model [2]. However, the ray-tracing method is too complex to simulate irregular scatterers. On the other hand, correlation-based channel model (CBM) has less computational complexity than the ray-tracing. However, the CBM can not capture the impact of the specific environment on the wireless channel. Trees are complex scatterers to simulate in the wireless channel model due to its changing status (e.g., the leaf on the tree moves, the small-scale characteristics of channel model may change). If the ray-tracing and CBM can combine, the irregular scatterer is feasible to be analyzed by ray-tracing based channel model.

In this paper, we report a hybrid channel model combining the ray-tracing model and the CBM. The ray-tracing model is used to compute the deterministic rays from base station (BS) to user equipment (UE). Moreover, the correlation-based model is used to compute the dynamic rays passing through foliage. The dynamic ray is the ray with time-variant characteristics following the tree status variation. In order to build the hybrid channel model, we propose parameters from the CBM to help the ray-tracing method reduce the

computational complexity while keeping the accuracy of the model.

II. HYBRID CHANNEL MODEL

In the particular case of propagation channel model, multipath components in the channel model can be divided into two types. The first type of rays are deterministic multipath components, e.g., the building and ground reflections. The second type of rays are dynamic multipath components, e.g., vehicles, trees, human scatterings. The dynamic rays are time-varying, while the deterministic rays are stationary. We consider N_t time slots and N_f samples of frequency in each simulation, $n_t = 1, 2, \dots, N_t$ and $n_f = 1, 2, \dots, N_f$. Then, the one of hybrid channel impulse response (CIR) of the wireless channel is expressed by

$$H(n_t, n_f) = \sum_{n_{st}=1}^{N_{st}} H_{n_{st},st}(n_f) + \sum_{n_{dy}=1}^{N_{dy}} H_{n_{dy},dy}(n_t, n_f), \quad (1)$$

where $H_{n_{st},st}(n_f)$ and $H_{n_{dy},dy}(n_t, n_f)$ denote CIR of the n_{st} -th deterministic and the n_{dy} -th dynamic ray at the n_t -th time slot and the n_f -th frequency sample, and N_{st} and N_{dy} denote numbers of deterministic and dynamic rays, respectively [3].

In this paper, we used a ray-tracing tool based on fundamental physical ray propagation property on the mmWave band to simulate the deterministic part of the wireless channel, i.e., $\sum_{n_{st}=1}^{N_{st}} H_{n_{st},st}(n_f)$ [4]. Then, the dynamic part of the wireless channel, i.e., $\sum_{n_{dy}=1}^{N_{dy}} H_{n_{dy},dy}(n_t, n_f)$, is generated by the CBM [5], where the power profile of time delay and Doppler spread are assumed to be Laplace distributed. According to the Wiener-Khinchin theorem, the autocorrelation of frequency and time are Fourier pair of the time delay and Doppler shift, respectively [6]. After the normalizing the power delay profile (PDP), the correlation of frequency is given by [5]

$$R_{f,n_{st}}(\Delta f) = \frac{P_{n_{st}} b_f^2}{b_f^2 + (2\pi\Delta f)^2} e^{-j2\pi\Delta f\tau_{n_{st}}}, \quad (2)$$

where $R_{f,n_{st}}(\Delta f)$ stands for correlation of frequency with n_{st} -th deterministic ray from tree received at UE, Δf is the difference of the frequency, b_f is tree relative parameter for frequency correlation, and $\tau_{n_{st}}$ and $P_{n_{st}}$ are the time delay and received power of n_{st} -th deterministic ray from tree received at UE, respectively. The correlation of time is shown in equation (3) which derivation method is similar to the correction of frequency. However, the exponential part in the correlation of time is ignored because the initial Doppler shift in the communication system is 0.

$$R_t(\Delta t) = \frac{b_t^2}{b_t^2 + (2\pi\Delta t)^2}, \quad (3)$$

where $R_t(\Delta t)$ stands for correlation of time, Δt is the difference of the time, b_t is tree relative parameter for time correlation. Parameters $P_{n_{st}}$, $\tau_{n_{st}}$, b_f , and b_t capture the impact of the practical environment. $P_{n_{st}}$, and $\tau_{n_{st}}$ including the information of n_{st} -th deterministic ray from tree to UE are computed by the ray-tracing method. The power radiated from the BS to the UE via the tree is quantified by the radar cross section (RCS) scattering model. The RCS value of a tree in the simulation is assumed to be 10 dBsm [7].

After obtaining $R_t(\Delta t)$ and $R_f, n_{st}(\Delta f)$ for dynamic channel with the deterministic ray information, the CIR of dynamic rays from tree to UE can be computed by

$$\mathbf{H}_{n_{dy}, dy} = \mathbf{R}_t^{\frac{1}{2}} \mathbf{H}_{i.i.d.} \mathbf{R}_f^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{i.i.d.}$ is a $N_t \times N_f$ independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) complex Gaussian random matrix. For a matrix \mathbf{A} , we denote $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{A}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, as long as $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{B}^H$.

III. PARAMETERS OF TREES

The b_f and b_t are two tree-related parameters from the correlation model based on the practical environment. In the real world, the range of time delay spread for dynamic rays is dependent on the size of the tree. In order to control the range of time delay spread in the CBM, the parameter b_f is based on the size of the tree. The equation (5) shows the method to compute the b_f . T_f is the parameter to decide the shape of the Laplace distribution, which is pertinent to dynamic CIR shape. The T_f is denoted to the threshold of frequency. Furthermore, the fluctuation of the time-variant channel of dynamic rays is dependent on the velocity of leaf moving. Hence, the b_t is based on leaf moving velocity to controls the fluctuation range of dynamic rays. The equation (5) shows the method to compute the b_t . T_t is the parameter to decide the fluctuation of power or phase variation range in the dynamic time-variant channel. The T_t is denoted to threshold of time. These two parameters build up a link between the different tree status or size and the channel performance. Therefore, these parameters help CBM overcome it drawback.

$$T_f = e^{-b_f |\Delta\tau|}, T_t = e^{-b_t |\Delta\omega|}, \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta\tau$ is the difference of the time delay, and $\Delta\omega$ is the difference of the Doppler shift frequency in radians. T_t and T_f are assigned as 0.1 in this paper.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

System models in an urban area for line-of-sight (LOS) and non-LOS (NLOS) scenarios are shown in Fig. 1 (a) and (b), respectively. The shape of building is assumed to be a 60 m \times 60 m square, and the width of street is assumed to be 7 m [8]. In this system, 4 reference UEs are considered and there are located at point 1, 2, 3, and 4. The reference point 1, 2, and 3 are set for LOS scenario and the reference point 4 is set for NLOS scenario. The coordinate of these points are (22, 61), (33, 66), (44,61), and (0,64), respectively. In the simulating channel environment, we considered the direct ray, first- and second-order reflection ray from BS to UE, and the first-order reflection ray from tree to UE. Additionally,

Fig. 1: The map of system model

TABLE I: Main simulation assumption [2]

Parameter name	Parameter value
Frequency (GHz)	28
Transmitter power (W)	1
Antenna gain (dBi)	5.8
BS and tree height (m)	3
UE height (m)	1.5
b_f	4×10^8
b_t	2

the relative permittivity of the buildings in the ray-tracing is 4.44 [1]. Taking point 1 as the example point, for convenient description, is shown in Fig. 1 (a). Rays from BS to point 1, point 4, and tree are used black wire to express and rays from the tree to point 1, and 4 are used green wire to express in Fig. 1. Black rays are deterministic rays containing large-scale characteristics of propagation channel computed by using the ray-tracing method and green rays are dynamic rays containing small-scale characteristics of propagation channel computed by using the correlation method based on ray-tracing results from tree to UE. After the description of key parameters design and dynamic hybrid system model, the set scenario of LOS and NLOS will be used to simulate. The main simulation assumptions are summarized in Table I.

The LOS impulse response combining deterministic and dynamic rays is shown in Fig. 2 (a). The deterministic and dynamic rays can be distinguished well because the time difference between these two types of rays is more than 0.1 ms. The multipath components of deterministic rays for point 1, 2, and 3 can be distinguished well due to a 10 ns delay resolution. It is observed that the power of deterministic ray is higher than dynamic rays. The fastest and strongest ray for these received point is the direct ray from BS to UE. When the ray is passing through the tree, the power of the signal is attenuated about 60 dB compared to that of the direct ray. In Fig. 2 (b), the time delay of deterministic and dynamic rays have a similar value at NLOS situation. Therefore, the delay spread range of dynamic rays has an overlap the time delay of deterministic rays. Moreover, there are some fluctuations on the deterministic impulse response. However, the first- and second-order reflection of deterministic rays at NLOS situation can be distinguished. The fluctuation before the first

Fig. 2: The impulse response of the LOS and NLOS

(a) LOS power 28 GHz (point 1) (b) NLOS power 28 GHz (point 4)

(c) LOS phase (point 1) (d) NLOS phase (point 4)

Fig. 3: The value of channel power and phase variation with time changing at 27.7 GHz and 28 GHz

deterministic ray is caused by the direct ray passing through the tree from BS to UE. The power of dynamic ray is about 50 dB below the strongest deterministic ray. Comparing to the LOS situation, the power level of NLOS for deterministic and dynamic rays are similar in these two situations because two first- and second-order reflection rays in NLOS situation will have the same phase causing rays constructive addition at the point 4.

The channel variation with time is shown in Fig. 3. According to Fig. 3 (a) and (b), the received power changing is limited because the leaf on the branch only can move small distance. Hence, it cannot have a big influence of the channel performance. In Fig. 3 (c) and (d), the phase changing is related to the value of the operation frequency. When the multipath components combine, received power and phase variations due to the constructive and destructive addition of multipath signal components dependent on the frequency and distance of transmitter and receiver. If the set operation frequency and scenario result in rays destructive

(a) Point 1 (b) Point 4

Fig. 4: The channel model performance with time variation of different frequencies at point 1 and 4.

addition, a deep fading happens in this scenario. When the simulation frequency is at the deep fading part, the phase and the received power change range will increase. The proposed channel model performance with time variation of different frequencies at different scenarios are shown in Fig. 4. The channel variation with time changing can be seen clearly in Fig. 4. Since the phase change at point 4 scenario is smaller than that of point 1, the received power variation of point 4 is smaller than that of point 1.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The ray-tracing based dynamic channel model with the tree at 28 GHz is described and analyzed in this paper. The hybrid model combines the ray-tracing and CBM and provides a balance of accuracy and complexity. The characteristics of time-varying channel are captured by the proposed model. The channel performance of the proposed model with time variation is shown. In the future, parameters b_f and b_t will be extracted from practical measurements. Moreover, general urban scenarios will be taken into account.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research is funded in part by EUROSTARS Project BuildWise (11088), and in part by the H2020-MSCA IF-AceLSAA (752644).

REFERENCES

- [1] T. S. Rappaport *et al.*, "Millimeter wave wireless communications," Pearson Education, 2014
- [2] J. Lee *et al.*, "Improving the accuracy of millimeter-wave ray-tracing simulations by modeling roadside trees," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 162-166, Jan. 2019.
- [3] J. Zhang *et al.*, "An Experimental Study on Indoor Massive 3D-MIMO Channel at 30-40 GHz Band," *2018 ISAP*, Korea (South), 2018, pp. 1-2.
- [4] G. Liang *et al.*, "A new approach to 3-D ray tracing for propagation prediction in cities," *IEEE Trans. on Antennas Propag.*, vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 853-863, June 1998.
- [5] J. Zhang, "Spatial correlation coefficient estimator for frequency selective MIMO channels," *Electron. Lett.*, vol. 55, no. 5, pp. 290-292, Mar. 2019.
- [6] G. D. Durgin, "Space-time wireless channels," *Prentice Hall PTR*, pp. 48, 2003.
- [7] R. Caldeirinha *et al.*, "A novel FDTD based model for prediction of bistatic RCS of single leaves and trees," *2001 Eleventh ICAP*, UK, 2001, pp. 783-786.
- [8] L. Rachowski *et al.*, "METIS channel models, deliverable 1.4 v.1.3," METIS Project, Tech. Rep. ICT-317669, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://www.metis2020.com/>